

COMPENSATING REFLECTOR DEFORMATIONS EXPLOITING DIGITAL BEAMFORMING IN ARRAY FED REFLECTOR ANTENNAS

Martin Togstad^{1,2}, George Goussetis², Francesco Lisi^{2,3}, Hervé Legay³, Leri Datashvili¹

⁽¹⁾ Large Space Structures GmbH
Munich, Germany
Email: {martin.togstad, leri.datashvili}@largespace.de

⁽²⁾ Heriot-Watt University
Edinburgh, UK
Email: {mt4022, f.lisi, g.goussetis}@hw.ac.uk

⁽³⁾ Thales Alenia Space
Toulouse, France
Email: {francesco.lisi, herve.legay}@thalesaleniaspace.com

Abstract—Spaceborne reflector antennas are critical in satellite missions but are sensitive to structural deformations from manufacturing tolerances and thermoelastic effects in orbit. Even small errors can degrade gain, sidelobes, and pointing. Array-fed reflectors (AFRs), combining a parabolic reflector with a digitally beamformed phased array feed, provide flexibility in beam shaping and enable digital-domain correction of such distortions.

In this work, we analyse a representative AFR system subject to random surface errors modeled by Zernike polynomials. A Monte Carlo study quantifies the effect of distortions on antenna gain, and a matched filtering strategy is applied to compensate them. The results show that digital beamforming can recover performance without mechanical intervention, enhancing the robustness of reflector-based satellite antennas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Large deployable reflectors (LDRs) are widely used in satellite communications and remote sensing. Their main advantage is high gain, but their performance is sensitive to surface distortions caused by manufacturing tolerances, deployment errors, and thermoelastic effects in orbit. Such deformations lead to reduced gain, increased sidelobes, and pointing errors [4].

Array-fed reflectors (AFRs) combine a parabolic reflector with a digital feed. In addition to enabling multi-beam operation, AFRs allow digital control of the feed excitations. This flexibility makes it possible to mitigate the impact of reflector distortions at the signal processing stage [3], [1]. A simple sketch of the system considered in this work is shown in Fig. 1, including the offset parabolic reflector and the 91-element feed array.

Fig. 1. System architecture.

In this paper, reflector surface errors are modeled using Zernike polynomials [5]. Random coefficients are generated and scaled to prescribed root-mean-square (RMS) values. A Monte Carlo procedure is used to generate multiple independent distortions for each RMS level.

Matched filtering (MF), also known as conjugate field matching, is adopted as the compensation method. The MF weights are derived from the undeformed reference reflector and applied to the deformed surfaces. The performance is evaluated in terms of gain relative to the ideal case.

The main outcome is the statistical relationship between reflector RMS error and antenna gain obtained with MF compensation. These results are compared to the theoretical prediction from Ruze's formula.

II. REFLECTOR DEFORMATION MODELING

The antenna under study is an offset parabolic reflector with a diameter of $D = 2,4$ m, focal length $f = 4,423$ m, and offset $x_c = 3,1$ m. The operating frequency is 11.7 GHz, corresponding to a wavelength of $\lambda \simeq 25,6$ mm. The undeformed surface is defined analytically by the parent paraboloid

$$z(x, y) = \frac{x^2 + y^2}{4f}. \quad (1)$$

A 91-element digital array is placed at a 0,54 m offset towards the reflector from the focal point, as shown in Fig. 1.

A. Zernike Polynomial Distortions

Surface deformations are represented with Zernike polynomials $Z_n^m(\rho, \theta)$ on the unit disk [5]. The coefficients are indexed in a row-major order, according to the pyramid shown in Fig. 2. In this scheme, piston is the first coefficient at the top of the pyramid, followed by the two tilt terms on the second row, and then astigmatism and defocus on the third row.

Fig. 2. Zernike polynomial pyramid with indexing.

There are 62 ($66 - 4$) active coefficients that make up the reflector surface distortions. To isolate pure shape errors, piston, tilts, and defocus are excluded from the randomisation process. The remaining coefficients are assigned random values and scaled to produce the desired RMS surface error.

B. Randomisation and RMS Scaling

Randomised surface errors are generated by assigning zero-mean coefficients to the selected Zernike modes. A Gaussian distribution is applied to the coefficients. The resulting deformation field is scaled to a target RMS error. The RMS is computed over the circular aperture mask as

$$\text{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (z_{\text{def}}(x_i, y_i) - z_{\text{ref}}(x_i, y_i))^2}, \quad (2)$$

where z_{ref} is the sag of the undeformed paraboloid and z_{def} is the sag after applying the Zernike distortion.

Given a random coefficient vector \mathbf{r} and a target RMS value σ_{mm} (in millimetres), the coefficients are rescaled according to

$$s = \frac{\sigma_{\text{mm}}/1000}{\text{RMS}(\mathbf{r})}, \quad \mathbf{c} = s \mathbf{r}, \quad (3)$$

so that the final scaled coefficients \mathbf{c} produce a surface error with the prescribed RMS value.

C. Monte Carlo Procedure

For each RMS level, multiple independent realisations are generated by drawing new sets of random coefficients. This Monte Carlo framework allows the statistical impact of distortions to be quantified, following approaches similar to [4], [2]. The resulting distributions of antenna gain are presented in Section IV.

In the simulations, the following parameters were used:

- RMS values (mm):

$$\{0, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0\},$$

- Number of independent realisations per RMS level: $N_{\text{iter}} = 10$,
- Steering directions (elevation θ , azimuth ϕ in degrees):

θ	ϕ
0.0	0.0
2.5	0.0
2.5	45.0
2.5	90.0
2.5	135.0
2.5	180.0

D. Example: 2 mm RMS Distortion

To illustrate the procedure, Fig. 3 shows a random realisation of the reflector surface error with a target RMS of 2 mm. The distortions originate from the Zernike pyramid in Fig. 2, and their amplitude reaches several millimetres across the aperture.

Fig. 3. Reflector surface distortion generated with randomised Zernike coefficients scaled to an RMS of 2 mm.

The far-field of the undistorted reference reflector is shown in Fig. 4. The main beam is symmetric, and the maximum gain reaches the nominal value close to 46,3 dBi.

Fig. 4. Far-field pattern of the undistorted reflector (0 mm RMS).

When the 2 mm RMS distortion is applied, the far-field changes as shown in Fig. 5. The peak gain drops to around 45,68 dB and the sidelobe structure becomes irregular, reflecting the random phase errors introduced across the aperture.

Fig. 5. Far-field pattern of the distorted reflector of Fig. 3 (2 mm RMS and MF compensation).

A direct comparison of the patterns is provided in Fig. 6, which shows a cut at $\phi = 0^\circ$. The red curve corresponds to the undistorted reflector, the blue curve to the distorted reflector with the original weights, and the green curve to the distorted reflector with MF compensation.

Fig. 6. Far-field comparison at $\phi = 0^\circ$: undistorted (red, 46,3 dBi), distorted with original weights (blue, 42,4 dBi), and distorted with MF compensation (green, 45,7 dBi).

The uncompensated distorted reflector exhibits a clear loss in peak gain and elevated sidelobe levels. With MF compensation, most of the lost gain is recovered and the main beam approaches the reference case, although residual sidelobe distortions remain.

III. DIGITAL BEAMFORMING COMPENSATION APPROACH

Compensation is performed using MF [1]. For a given steering direction, the excitation vector for each individual feed in the array is defined as

$$\mathbf{w}_{MF} = \mathbf{e}^*, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{e} denotes the complex electric field in a given direction and \mathbf{w}_{MF} is the complex conjugate of \mathbf{e} , which is reapplied as a weight for a given feed in the array.

Two weighting strategies are compared:

- **Distorted MF (maximum-gain reference):** MF weights are computed from the distorted reflector itself, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_{def} = \mathbf{e}_{def}^*$. This provides the maximum possible gain for the deformed surface and serves as a performance upper bound [3].
- **Reference MF (compensation test):** MF weights are computed once from the undeformed reflector, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_{ref} = \mathbf{e}_{r141592ef}^*$, and then applied to all deformed realisations. This tests how well the undeformed weights preserve the desired beam in the presence of surface errors.

By comparing these two cases, the recovery in main beam gain due to digital compensation can be quantified. The Reference MF weights remain fixed for all randomised distortion realisations and new MF weights are

computed for all randomised distortion realisations, ensuring that performance improvements can be attributed only to the digital beamforming process.

In this work, only matched filtering is evaluated. Other approaches, such as back projection are left for future study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The key result of this study is the statistical relationship between surface RMS error and antenna gain when MF is applied. Figure 7 shows the co-polar gain at the target direction as a function of RMS error, both at boresight and for five steering directions in Section II C. Solid curves represent the MF-compensated results, while dashed curves correspond to the uncompensated case. Each point is the mean of 10 Monte Carlo realisations, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. The solid black line shows Ruze's theoretical prediction, based on the formula for offset reflectors given in [2].

Fig. 7. Co-polar gain versus RMS surface error with matched filtering. Results are shown for boresight and five beam steering directions ($\theta = 2.5^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ, 180^\circ$). Solid lines correspond to MF compensation, dashed lines to the original uncompensated case. Error bars indicate the standard deviation across Monte Carlo realisations. The black solid curve shows Ruze's prediction.

At boresight, the uncompensated gain decreases from about 46 dBi at 0 mm RMS to below 36 dBi at 3 mm RMS, closely following Ruze's curve. With MF, the gain remains above 45 dBi across the full range, with a decline of less than 1 dB up to 3 mm RMS.

For the off-boresight beams ($\theta = 2.5^\circ$), the uncompensated loss exceeds 10 dB at 3 mm RMS, while with MF the gain stays near 44–45 dBi with only a slight downward slope. This shows that MF reduces the sensitivity to surface errors compared to the Ruze reference.

The error bars indicate that variability grows with RMS, negligible at < 0.5 mm but several dB at 2–3 mm, especially for the uncompensated case. Overall, MF compensation maintains high gain for both boresight and steered beams, and its advantage becomes more pronounced as distortions increase.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the effect of reflector surface distortions on an array-fed offset reflector antenna at 11.7 GHz. The distortions were introduced using randomised Zernike polynomials scaled to prescribed RMS values, and their impact was quantified through Monte Carlo simulations.

Digital compensation was performed using matched filtering. The main performance metric was the co-polar gain at the target direction. The results show that:

- Uncompensated gain follows Ruze's prediction, decreasing rapidly with RMS error, while MF maintains significantly higher gain.
- At boresight, the uncompensated gain drops by more than 10 dB at 3 mm RMS, whereas MF keeps the loss below 1 dB.
- For steered beams, uncompensated degradation exceeds 10 dB at high RMS values, but MF keeps the gain near 44–45 dBi with only a slight slope.
- Variability across random realisations increases with RMS, but MF consistently improves both the mean gain and robustness.

Overall, matched filtering provides an effective digital-domain compensation strategy, maintaining high gain levels even at large RMS errors and achieving performance beyond the conventional Ruze prediction.

Future work will consider alternative beamforming strategies, such as back projection, to provide a broader comparison of compensation methods, as well as approaches for handling unknown surface distortions.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. J. Acosta, "Compensation of reflector surface distortions using conjugate field matching," in *Proc. IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society Int. Symp.*, Philadelphia, PA, USA, Jun. 1986, pp. 390–393, doi: 10.1109/APS.1986.1149756.
- [2] P. Nielsen, T. Rubæk, and H.-H. Viskum, "Random surface distortion in GRASP," TICRA, Copenhagen, Denmark, White Paper, Issue 1.0, Jun. 2020. Available: <https://www.ticra.com>
- [3] Y. Rahmat-Samii, "Novel array-feed distortion compensation techniques for reflector antennas," *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 14–22, Mar. 1991, doi: 10.1109/62.73776.
- [4] X. Xiang, Y. Xu, and Z. Zhang, "Effect of surface error distribution and aberration on electromagnetic performance of a reflector antenna," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2019, Article ID 5062545, pp. 1–8, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1155/2019/5062545.
- [5] K. Niu and C. Tian, "Zernike polynomials and their applications," *Journal of Optics*, vol. 24, no. 12, 123001, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1088/2040-8986/ac9e08.